

1 **Title:** The helper strategy in vector-transmission of plant viruses

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15 **Abstract**

16 An intriguing aspect of vector-transmission of plant viruses is the very frequent involvement
17 of a helper component (HC). HCs are virus-encoded non-structural proteins produced in
18 infected plant cells that are mandatory for the transmission success. Over five decades, all
19 data collected on HCs from unrelated viral species transmitted by distinct vector species
20 were consistent with a unique mode of action designated “the bridge hypothesis”: the HC
21 has two functional domains, one binding the virus particle and the other binding a putative
22 receptor in the vector, thus creating a reversible molecular bridge between the two. This
23 hypothesis appeared fully satisfactory as HCs were reported solely in viruses transmitted
24 non-circulatively -- *i.e.* the virus particle binds externally to the mouthpart of its vector, and
25 can later be released thereof and inoculated. Recently, however, HCs have also been
26 reported in viruses transmitted circulatively, where the virus particles are internalized in gut
27 cells and cycle within the body to reach the salivary glands. In this more complicated
28 scheme of virus-vector interaction, a simple mode of action of HC compatible with the bridge
29 hypothesis becomes questionable. In addition, while it had consistently been shown that the
30 sequential acquisition of HC and virus particles could only work when HC was acquired first,
31 a recent report shows that the reverse acquisition sequence can work in some case, again
32 questioning the bridge hypothesis as a universal mode of action. Because of the importance
33 of HC molecules in the vector-transmission of plant viruses, we here propose an exhaustive
34 review of the field, of its historical perspective and most recent development.

35

36 **1 Introduction**

37 Vector transmission is the mean by which most plant viruses (around 80% - (Kassanis and
38 Govier 1971; Lung and Pirone 1973) ensure plant-to-plant transfer, and thus maintenance and
39 spread in the environment. Any organism feeding on/in plants and capable of moving from
40 one plant to another can uptake and release viruses and can thus potentially act as a vector.
41 Very diverse organisms (protists, nematodes, mites and insects) have been reported as
42 efficient vectors, but sap feeding hemipteran insects encompassing plant hoppers, leaf
43 hoppers, and particularly whiteflies and aphids are by far the most important (Nault 1997; Ng
44 and Perry 2004; Hogenhout, Ammar et al. 2008). The mechanisms of virus-vector interaction
45 are also very diverse and have been extensively studied in hemipteran insects, which are thus
46 the major focus of this review. Nevertheless, the current classification of the transmission
47 modes of hemipteran insect-transmitted viruses can accommodate cases of transmission by
48 all types of vectors, including mites, nematodes and even protists (Blanc 2008).

49 The two major transmission categories are named non-circulative and circulative (Blanc,
50 Drucker and Uzest 2014). The non-circulative transmission qualifies cases where the plant-
51 vector interaction is exclusively external. In hemipteran vectors, the virus reversibly binds to
52 the mouthparts and/or the foregut, where it can be retained for a short time (few minutes to
53 hours) and immediately inoculated to another plant upon salivation or regurgitation. In
54 contrast, the circulative transmission corresponds to cases where the interaction is internal.
55 In hemipteran vectors, this means that the virus crosses the gut and circulates within the insect
56 body to reach the salivary glands and ultimately the saliva. Whatever the details of this cycle,
57 it involves an initial specific recognition and the crossing of one or several cellular barriers (at
58 least gut and salivary glands) to accumulate within and be secreted out of the vector. The
59 consequences are the existence of a latent period between acquisition and inoculation, and
60 also, in all reported cases, a high and long-lasting accumulation of the virus that can be
61 transmitted for the whole vector's life span (Blanc, Drucker and Uzest 2014). The circulative
62 transmission is divided in the propagative and non-propagative sub-categories depending on
63 whether the virus replicates or not during its cycle within the vector (Blanc and Gutierrez 2015).

64 Regarding molecular interactions with the vector, plant viruses have seemingly evolved two
65 distinct strategies, the "capsid strategy" and the "helper strategy" (Pirone and Blanc 1996). In
66 the capsid strategy, the virus particles are necessary and sufficient to ensure the specific
67 recognition of the vector. The experimental demonstration came from the capacity of the
68 corresponding viruses to be directly acquired from suspensions of purified virus particles,
69 without any other viral proteins, and later transmitted to healthy host plants (Pirone 1964),

70 demonstrating that the coat protein alone can control attachment (and cycle) within the vector.
71 However, all viruses are not transmissible this way. In addition to the virus particle, a virus-
72 encoded non-structural protein is mandatory for the helper strategy. A large number of viral
73 species have been shown to require such additional proteins that have been designated
74 “helper components” (HC). Since the first case report for a species of the genus *Potyvirus*
75 (Kassanis and Govier 1971b), HCs have been described in many other non-circulative virus
76 genera and the helper strategy proved dominant in this transmission category (Syller 2006).
77 Because HCs of unrelated viruses have no sequence homologies, a specific definition has
78 been provided by (Froissart, Michalakis et al. 2002): “a HC can be any compound complying
79 with all of the following criteria: (i) it is virus-encoded, (ii) it can be one or a complex of several
80 non-structural molecules (i.e., which can be eliminated upon purification of virions), (iii) it is
81 necessary for the success of vector transmission, and (iv) HC and virions can be acquired
82 sequentially by the vector”.

83 Until today, the HCs from unrelated plant viruses were thought to have the same mode of
84 action, illustrating a convergent evolution, although the selective advantage they may provide
85 remains totally speculative (Pirone et Blanc 1996; Froissart, Michalakis et al. 2002). One
86 unexplained longstanding observation was the fact that the helper strategy appears frequent
87 in non-circulative transmission but extremely rare in circulative transmission (Franz, van der
88 Wilk et al. 1999). Recent advances are challenging these views by showing that the helper
89 strategy appears widespread in all transmission categories (Grigoras, Vetten et al. 2018; Lu,
90 Li et al. 2019; Di Mattia, Vernerey et al. 2020), and that distinct HCs may have different modes
91 of action (Di Mattia, Torralba et al. 2022). In this review, we confront the historical context and
92 the recent discoveries, and we discuss how this wealth of knowledge indicates that HCs may
93 have evolved for diverse reasons in distinct viral clades.

94 **2 An historical perspective on the discovery of helper components**

95 The discovery of HCs and the characterization of their mode of action results exclusively from
96 studies of non-circulatively transmitted viruses. Indeed, as already mentioned above, that the
97 helper strategy also exist in circulative viruses is a very recent finding; it is poorly characterized
98 and will be discussed in a later specific section.

99 The first hint on the discovery of HCs came from (Pirone and Megahed 1966) who observed
100 that purified particles of *Cauliflower mosaic virus* (CaMV) or *Turnip mosaic virus* (TuMV) were
101 not transmissible, when acquired through parafilm membranes by aphid vectors. At that time
102 the explanation was unclear and could as well be attributed to partial degradation of virions
103 during the purification process. However, about five years later, key complementary
104 information was reported on the same viral genera. In a series of experiments based on

105 sequential acquisition of transmissible and non-transmissible natural isolates, Govier &
106 Kassanis, and in parallel Lung and Pirone, respectively set the basis of the concept of HC for
107 potyviruses (*Potato virus Y*, PVY) and caulimoviruses (CaMV) (**Table 1**). These authors first
108 demonstrated that a non-transmissible isolate could be efficiently transmitted by aphids
109 previously fed on a plant infected with a transmissible isolate of the same viral species, and
110 that the reverse acquisition sequence did not work (Kassanis and Govier 1971a; Kassanis
111 and Govier 1971b; Lung and Pirone 1973). These experiments pointed to the existence of a
112 helper factor that would be produced in the plants infected by the transmissible isolate. Such
113 a helper factor could be acquired first by aphids and somewhat be retained and “wait”
114 somewhere in the alimentary tract to complement the transmission of the secondarily acquired
115 non-transmissible isolate. The same authors consistently showed that the transmission of
116 purified virus particles of both poty- and caulimoviruses could be rescued by pre-feeding
117 aphids onto plants infected with a transmissible isolates (Govier and Kassanis 1974; Lung and
118 Pirone 1974). Potyvirus-infected plant extracts deprived of virus particles by ultracentrifugation
119 contained HC activity, indicating that the HC is not the virus particle of the transmissible isolate
120 itself (Govier and Kassanis 1974). Additional chemical, biochemical and immunological
121 treatments of potyvirus-infected plant extracts further demonstrated that the HC is a non
122 structural protein produced upon infection of plants by a transmissible isolate (Govier,
123 Kassanis et al. 1977). Antisera directed against viral proteins produced from cell-free
124 translation of viral RNA provided the first hint that the HC is virus-encoded by specifically
125 blocking its activity in infected plant-extracts (Thornbury and Pirone 1983). The copurification
126 of potyviral HC activity and of a viral polypeptide of around 50 KDa further pointed in the same
127 direction (Thornbury, Hellmann et al. 1985). Nevertheless, it was not before the development
128 of molecular biology, particularly the sequencing technology and the production of infectious
129 clones allowing reverse genetic approaches, that the viral origin of HCs could be definitely
130 and directly proven.

131 Potyvirus

132 The genome of potyviruses is a ss(+)RNA encoding one single large polyprotein precursor,
133 post-translationally cleaved in ten polypeptides each with one or more specific functions
134 (Allison, Sorenson et al. 1985, Domier, Franklin et al. 1986, Dougherty and Carrington 1988).
135 The polypeptide co-purifying with the HC activity (Thornbury, Hellmann et al. 1985) was
136 identified as the second from the N-ter of the polyprotein (Carrington, Cary et al. 1989).
137 Because it also possesses a protease activity, releasing it from the precursor large
138 polyprotein, it was named the helper component proteinase (HC-Pro) (Carrington, Freed et al.
139 1989). Comparison of HC-Pro sequences from transmissible and non-transmissible species
140 and isolates pointed at differences in two key regions. The first is located in the N-ter region

141 (AA positions 50-54) where a conserved “KITC” motif is mutated to EITC in non-transmissible
142 isolates (Thornbury, Patterson et al. 1990; Granier, Durand-Tardif et al. 1993; Canto, Lopez-
143 Moya et al. 1995). The second is located in the central region (AA positions 308-310) where
144 a conserved “PTK” motif is mutated to PAK in non-transmissible isolates (Huet, Gal-On et al.
145 1994). The key role of both motifs in HC activity has been thoroughly confirmed by reverse
146 genetics where the introduction of these mutations in transmissible infectious clones always
147 abolished their capacity to be transmitted by aphids (Atreya, Atreya et al. 1992; Atreya and
148 Pirone 1993; Huet, Gal-On et al. 1994).

149 Caulimovirus

150 The comparison of CaMV sequences revealed that the non-transmissible isolate CM4-184
151 harbors a 421 bp deletion in the coding region II (gene II) (Howell and Hull 1978; Howarth,
152 Gardner et al. 1981). These authors thereby established that gene II was dispensable for plant
153 infection, pointing at its specific function in aphid transmission. This was soon confirmed by
154 the demonstration that deletion and/or mutation of this genome region in transmissible CaMV
155 isolates were associated with the loss of transmissibility (Armour, Melcher et al. 1983;
156 Daubert, Shepherd et al. 1983; Woolston, Covey et al. 1983; Woolston, Czaplewski et al.
157 1987). The product of gene II, the protein P2, has then been produced in the heterologous
158 baculovirus/insect cell system (Espinoza, Usmany et al. 1992) in a biologically active form
159 able to complement the transmission of CaMV non-transmissible isolates acquired from
160 infected plants or crude extracts thereof (Blanc, Cerutti et al. 1993). Intriguingly, this
161 heterologous-expressed P2 failed to complement the transmission of purified CaMV particle,
162 suggesting the possible requirement for an additional unknown factor (Blanc, Cerutti et al.
163 1993). Finally, this additional compound was identified as the viral protein P3 (product of gene
164 III) that must be present in the purified CaMV particle suspension for successful
165 complementation of aphid-transmission by the previously acquired P2 (Leh, Jacquot et al.
166 1999). Thus, two non-structural proteins, P2 and P3, assist the vector transmission of CaMV.
167 While P2 meets the four criteria defining a HC (Froissart, Michalakis et al. 2002), P3 does not.
168 Indeed, its acquisition together with CaMV virions is mandatory for successful vector
169 transmission (Drucker, Froissart et al. 2002). As P3 cannot be acquired separately from
170 virions, it cannot be qualified as a HC.

171 While the helper strategy has been extensively studied for the genera *Caulimovirus* and
172 *Potyvirus*, it has also been reported in other genera of the family *Potyviridae*, as for example
173 the *Ipomovirus* transmitted by whiteflies (Stenger, Hein et al. 2005; Stenger, Hein et al. 2006;
174 Young, Hein et al. 2007) and *Tritimovirus* transmitted by mites (Colinet, Kummert et al. 1998)
175 (**Table 1**). The requirement of HC molecules has even been evidenced in the genus
176 *Tobravirus* transmitted by nematodes in a non-circulative manner (MacFarlane, Vassilakos et

177 al. 1999) (**Table 1**). Hence, helper components appear to have evolved in unrelated viruses
178 transmitted non-circulatively by distinct vectors. Unfortunately, in depth characterization of
179 their mode of action remain limited to a few emblematic cases within the poty- and
180 caulimoviruses.

181 **3 Modes of action of helper components**

182 The repeated observation that successful transmission resulted either from the concomitant
183 acquisition of the HC and virus particle, or from their sequential acquisition solely if the HC is
184 acquired first, allowed the pioneer research groups working on potyviruses (Kassanis and
185 Govier 1971a; Kassanis and Govier 1971b) and caulimoviruses (Lung and Pirone 1973; Lung
186 and Pirone 1974) to propose an hypothesis describing the mode of action of HCs. The HC
187 would specifically bind to a receptor molecule within the vector and to the virus particle (or to
188 a viral partner fixed on the virus particle in the case of CaMV), through distinct functional
189 domains, thereby creating a molecular link between the two. This hypothesis, later named the
190 “bridge hypothesis” (Pirone and Blanc 1996) became widely accepted and, so far, nearly all
191 empirical investigations on the question yielded supportive results. Remarkably, very recent
192 data on the existence of HCs in circulative viral species is casting doubts or at least calling for
193 nuances and careful reexamination (see the dedicated section IV).

194

195 3.1 Helper component – virus particle interaction

196 Potyvirus

197 As indicated in the previous section, reverse genetic approaches identified two important
198 domains of the potyviral HC-Pro, respectively containing the motifs KITC and PTK. In parallel,
199 comparison of coat protein sequences pointed out at a highly conserved amino acid triplet
200 DAG that appears to be mutated to DAE in some of the analyzed non transmissible isolates
201 (Harrison and Robinson 1988). Directed mutagenesis in infectious clones of various potyviral
202 species, changing the triplet DAG to DAE, systematically resulted in the loss of aphid-
203 transmissibility (Atreya, Raccah et al. 1990; Gal-On, Antignus et al. 1992; Atreya, Lopez-Moya
204 et al. 1995). Noticeably, the DAG motif is located at the N-ter of the coat protein, in a region
205 predicted to be accessible at the surface of virus particle, thus potentially available for binding
206 to HC-Pro (Shukla and Ward 1989). The experimental demonstration of a direct interaction
207 between HC-Pro and the capsid of *Tobacco vein mottling virus* (TVMV) was obtained using a
208 protein blotting-overlay protocol where the HC-Pro extracted from infected plants was
209 assessed for specific binding onto full length or truncated coat protein. HC-Pro was shown to
210 interact with a 7 amino acid sequence (DTV DAGK) encompassing the DAG motif, and this
211 interaction was totally abolished by the DAE mutation. Several amino acid substitutions were

212 performed within the DTVDAGK sequence and used to demonstrate a perfect correlation
213 between HC-Pro/coat protein binding and successful aphid transmission (Blanc, Lopez-Moya
214 et al. 1997)(Figure 1). The HC-Pro-CP interaction was then reported for other potyviruses
215 (Peng, Kadoury et al. 1998) and the PTK amino acid triplet identified as the HC-Pro motif
216 recognizing the DAG of the coat protein (Peng, Kadoury et al. 1998)(Figure 1). Further
217 experimental evidence came from a study on the specificity of the binding between HC-Pro
218 and CP. The HC-Pro of zucchini yellow mosaic virus (ZYMV) cannot complement the
219 transmission of TuMV particles, and *vice versa*. Replacing the N-terminal region of the coat
220 protein of ZYMV by that of TuMV allowed the aphid transmission of the recombinant virus
221 complemented by the HC-Pro of TuMV (Dombrovsky, Gollop et al. 2007). This result strongly
222 suggested that the N-terminal region of the CP containing the DAG motif is the sole
223 determinant of the binding of potyvirus particles to HC-Pro (Figure 1).

224 Caulimovirus

225 Protein overlay assays demonstrated a more complex situation for CaMV (Schmidt, Blanc et
226 al. 1994). The HC (the protein P2) efficiently attached virions from infected plant crude extracts
227 but not from purified virus suspensions. The mandatory additional component eliminated upon
228 purification was later found to be the viral protein P3 (Leh, Jacquot et al. 1999; Leh, Jacquot
229 et al. 2001; Drucker, Froissart et al. 2002) that decorates virus particles, with its C-terminal
230 part deeply anchored into pores opened in between capsid hexamers, and its N-terminal part
231 exposed at the surface and binding to P2 (Plisson, Uzest et al. 2005; Hoh, Uzest et al. 2010)
232 (Figure 1). It is remarkable that P3 adopts a tetrameric parallel conformation when free in
233 solution and a very different one when anchored to the virion, and that only the latter
234 conformation has an affinity for a functional multimeric form of P2 (Hébrard, Drucker et al.
235 2001; Hoh, Uzest et al. 2010). These studies further determined that the virion-bound P3 forms
236 a network of N-terminal antiparallel coiled-coil dimers that bind to a coiled coil trimer of the C-
237 terminal moiety of P2 (Figure 1; for details see (Hoh, Uzest et al. 2010) and references
238 therein).

239 3.2 Helper component – aphid receptor interaction

240 Potyvirus

241 In the case of potyviruses, seminal work by Bradley and Ganong (Bradley and Ganong 1955)
242 showed that irradiation, or chemical treatment with formaldehyde, of the stylet's tip of
243 viruliferous aphids inhibited subsequent inoculation of PVY, suggesting that the infectious
244 virus material was retained at the corresponding location. Consistently, autoradiography of
245 aphids that had acquired labeled virions as well as optical, electron, and more recently
246 fluorescent microscopy showed that, though potyviruses are detected throughout the

247 alimentary tract, they are mainly retained at the distal tip of the aphid stylets bundle (Ammar
248 1994; Wang, Ammuar et al. 1996; Mondal, Ghanim et al. 2021). Transmission assays with
249 various potyviruses and aphid species demonstrated that the transmission success depends
250 largely on the HC-Pro/aphid species combination, and this was considered a first indication of
251 the probable existence of specific receptors of HC-Pro within aphid stylets (Wang, Powell et
252 al. 1998).

253 We here again refer to the two conserved amino acid motifs, KITC and PTK, respectively
254 located in the N-terminal and central regions of HC-Pro. While, as indicated above, mutations
255 in the PTK motif abolish the binding to the coat protein (Huet, Gal-On et al. 1994), changes in
256 KITC motif (and even in a larger N-terminal domain) do not but instead impair retention within
257 the stylets (Blanc, Ammar et al. 1998) (Figure 1). Biochemical and structural analysis of HC-
258 Pro revealed its capacity to self-interact and form oligomers (Thornbury, Hellmann et al. 1985;
259 Plisson, Drucker et al. 2003; Ruiz-Ferrer, Boskovic et al. 2005). Ruiz-Ferrer and colleagues
260 (Ruiz-Ferrer, Boskovic et al. 2005) further speculated that this oligomerization drives a
261 geometrical arrangement and generates two functional domains, which could respectively
262 bind to virion and to a receptor in the stylets.

263 An elegant study, combining the electrical control of aphid feeding behavior and transmission
264 testing, demonstrated that the acquisition of a potyvirus is associated to ingestion of infected
265 plant cell content, whereas the inoculation is associated to salivation (Powell 2005). The food
266 canal where the sap is streaming up and the salivary canal where the saliva is streaming down
267 are separated all along the stylets but at the extreme distal tip where they fuse to form the
268 “common canal”. The authors thus logically concluded that the HC-Pro-virion complexes
269 should be retained in the common canal, because it is the only location in contact with both
270 ingested plant material and ejected saliva. Despite the fact that all available results are
271 compatible with the bridge hypothesis (Dombrovsky, Gollop et al. 2007; Fernandez-Calvino,
272 Goytia et al. 2010; Kamangar, Christiaens et al. 2019), the identity of the receptor of HC-Pro
273 within the common canal remains elusive. Stylets being cuticular tissues, cuticular proteins
274 are of course expected to play a role in potyvirus binding and represent the best receptor
275 candidates, but the proof is still lacking.

276 Caulimovirus

277 Just as for potyviruses, the domain of the CaMV P2 that recognizes the putative receptor
278 within the aphid stylets has been localized by mutagenesis approaches in the N-terminal
279 domain of the protein. In particular, the identity of the residue at amino acid position 6 appears
280 to be key for aphid/virus recognition. In the CaMV Cabb-BJI isolate, replacement of the
281 glutamine at this position by other residues differentially affected the transmission efficiency

282 by distinct aphid species. One of these mutants, where a tyrosine substituted for the glutamine,
283 named mutant P2-Rev5, could no longer be transmitted by any aphid species (Moreno,
284 Hebrard et al. 2005).

285 A major advance in this field of research came from the development of an efficient in vitro
286 binding assay between the heterologously-expressed CaMV P2 and dissected aphid maxillary
287 stylets (Uzest, Gargani et al. 2007). This system confirmed that the P2-Rev5 mutant does not
288 bind to the stylets whereas the wild type P2 is specifically retained within the common canal,
289 onto an unforeseen cuticular structure that has been named the “acrostyle” (Uzest, Gargani
290 et al. 2010)(Figure 1). Initially reported as displaying cuticular proteins at its surface, the
291 acrostyle has been further characterized and its proteome is now available (Webster, Thillier
292 et al. 2017; Webster, Pichon et al. 2018; Deshoux, Masson et al. 2020). Of important note is
293 the identification of proteins from the CPR and CPAP3 families, named Stylin-01 to Stylin-05,
294 that have one of their domains emerging and thus accessible at the surface of the acrostyle
295 (Figure 1). All of these proteins stand as prime receptor candidates for non-circulative viruses
296 and, consistently, Stylin-01 was shown to be involved in CaMV transmission and has been
297 proposed to act as receptor for this virus (Webster, Pichon et al. 2018) (Figure 1).
298 Unfortunately, cuticular proteins are very difficult to handle. Their biochemical and structural
299 properties are virtually unknown, and further effort is needed to achieve heterologous
300 production in a correctly folded and fully functional form. This technical bottleneck has been
301 holding for decades and has thus far precluded the definitive validation of HC–receptor
302 interaction. Breaking this lock would pave the way for the search of receptors of potyviruses
303 and/or cucumoviruses, potentially among the Stylins described in the acrostyle, and for the
304 development of antagonistic compounds able to specifically block virus-vector interactions.

305 As indicated earlier, studies of the HC mode of action in non-circulative virus clades other than
306 caulimo- and potyviruses are scarce. To briefly mention in the frame of this review, the reports
307 on HC-Pro in distinct genera of the family *Potyviridae*, transmitted by whiteflies or even mites,
308 all assume a mode of action similar to that in the genus *Potyvirus* transmitted by aphids
309 (Colinet, Kummert et al. 1998; Stenger, Hein et al. 2005; Stenger, Hein et al. 2006; Young,
310 Hein et al. 2007). Likewise, investigation of the mode of action of the HC in tobnaviruses
311 indicated that virus particles can be retained in the anterior part of the feeding apparatus of
312 nematode vectors only when a compatible HC is also present and associated to virions, again
313 supporting the bridge hypothesis (MacFarlane, Vassilakos et al. 1999; Vassilakos, Vellios et
314 al. 2001).

315

316 **Figure 1: Schematization of the HC mode of action for noncirculative viruses transmitted**
 317 **by aphids.** At the tip of the aphid stylets, the acrostyle harbors cuticular proteins named *Stylins*
 318 (left). All known *Stylet-HC-virus particle interactions* and the involved protein domains (when
 319 identified) are detailed in the magnifications on the right.

320

321 3.3 Transmission activation

322 At least the two best-studied groups of non-circulative viruses, potyviruses and
 323 caulimoviruses, have evolved a remarkably sophisticated cellular response to the feeding of
 324 the insect vectors on infected plants. This response results in the immediate formation of
 325 specific viral transmission morphs that are efficiently acquired by the vectors. In both cases,
 326 the helper component is a key player of this phenomenon that has been called “Transmission
 327 Activation” (TA; Drucker and Then 2015)).

328 Within infected plant cells, the three components of the CaMV transmissible complexes, P2,
 329 P3 and virions, are separated in distinct compartments. The immense majority of the virus
 330 particles are accumulated, most likely as P3-virion complexes, in several electron-dense
 331 inclusions that have been identified as the viral factories. P2 is not detectable in these viral
 332 factories. Instead, P2 entirely accumulates in one unique electron-lucent inclusion per infected
 333 cell, that also contain P3 and a few scattered virions (Drucker, Froissart et al. 2002), and that

334 is designated the transmission body (TB). A series of studies uncovered a phenomenon where
335 the CaMV can reversibly produce functional transmissible complexes, precisely when needed,
336 when aphids puncture plant cells and ingest a minute amount of their content (Martinière,
337 Gargani et al. 2009; Bak, Gargani et al. 2013; Martiniere, Bak et al. 2013). Upon puncturing
338 an infected plant, the stylets and/or secreted saliva trigger a plant response, likely involving
339 calcium fluctuation and ROS production, which is immediately hijacked by the virus. Within
340 less than ten seconds, the TB is first loaded with tubulin and then disintegrates and disperses
341 P2 all over the cell cytoplasm onto the microtubule network (Martiniere, Bak et al. 2013). Within
342 the same short time frame, P3-virion complexes are expelled from the viral factories and also
343 totally cover the microtubule network, likely associating with P2 (Bak, Gargani et al. 2013).
344 The authors showed that transmissible complexes thereby become accessible all over the cell
345 probed by an aphid vector, and further demonstrated that the situation reversed to the initial
346 stage within 5 minutes of aphid departure, with the reconstitution of genuine TB (Martiniere,
347 Bak et al. 2013) and virion-loaded viral factories (Bak, Gargani et al. 2013).

348 A comparable observation has been reported by the same research group for potyviruses
349 (Berthelot, Ducouso et al. 2019). While the phenomenon of transmission activation can be
350 considered analogous, the molecular/cellular processes involved are totally distinct (Berthelot,
351 Macia et al. 2019). In this case, both the virus particles of TuMV and the HC-Pro are
352 homogeneously distributed over the cytoplasm of infected plant cells. The signal of the aphid
353 puncture and its transduction by the plant, possibly also involving calcium spiking and ROS
354 production, induces an immediate oligomerization of HC-Pro, and this conformational change
355 appears to promote the formation of HC-Pro-virion complexes within the cell. The same study
356 again demonstrates that this phenomenon is reversible after a few minutes from the triggering
357 signal, with disappearance of the oligomeric forms of HC-Pro within infected tissues.

358 In the two cases, one may wonder why a virus would adopt such a complex “behavior” when
359 a constitutive production of transmissible complexes in infected tissues would appear easier
360 and efficient. The explanation provided by the authors is that viral proteins are often
361 multifunctional and have many duties to fulfill. For example, CaMV-P3 complexes also bind to
362 P1 for cell-to-cell and long-distance movement within the plant (Stavolone, Villani et al. 2005)
363 and the domain of P3 involved in binding to P1 is the same as that binding to P2. The HC-Pro
364 of potyviruses has multiple functions (Valli, Gallo et al. 2018), many of which may not be
365 compatible with the oligomeric form binding to the virus particles upon aphid punctures. In
366 simple words, the transmissible complexes may interfere with other step of the viral life cycle
367 and their transient appearance just when needed may alleviate the problem.

368 Whether TA is a general phenomenon that could be extended to the transmission of many
369 others viral species is a formidable avenue of research in the near future, even beyond plant

370 virology (Blanc, Drucker et al. 2014). Likewise, whether it is limited to non-circulative
371 transmission and more specifically whether HC molecules should always be involved is also
372 a relevant and stimulating question.

373 **4 The helper strategy in circulative viruses**

374 The helper strategy has long been believed to be restricted to the non-circulative transmission,
375 though no explanation could be provided. There was one report, mentioning the involvement
376 of an HC in the aphid transmission of a nanovirus (Genus *Nanovirus*, Family *Nanoviridae*;
377 Franz, van der Wilk et al. 1999), but the molecular details were not investigated for nearly two
378 decades. This uncharacterized HC controlling the transmission of a circulative non-
379 propagative nanovirus thus remained the exception confirming the rule until very recently. The
380 discovery of the involvement of a HC in the leafhopper transmission of the circulative
381 propagative rice stripe virus (RSV, genus *Tenuivirus* Family *Phenuiviridae*, Order
382 *Bunyavirales*) definitely confirmed that a helper strategy can evolve whatever the category of
383 virus-vector interaction (Table 1). An interesting and timely question is now whether the bridge
384 hypothesis stands as the universal mode of action of HCs.

385 *Tenuiviruses*

386 Most members of the order *Bunyavirales* have a lipid envelope associated with two
387 glycoproteins Gn and Gc involved in membrane fusion and entry into host cells (Guardado-
388 Calvo and Rey 2017). Tenuiviruses appear to have lost their lipid envelop but still produce the
389 two glycoproteins, which are in this case non-structural proteins respectively named NSvc2-N
390 and NSvc2-C (Chen, Dessau et al. 2019), deriving from the cleavage of the precursor
391 glycoprotein NSvc2. The non-enveloped virus particles appear as filamentous
392 ribonucleoproteins (Toriyama 1986) and, interestingly, they cannot be transmitted by their
393 plant hopper vectors when purified (Lu, Li et al. 2019). The adjunction of the two glycoproteins
394 to purified ribonucleoproteins efficiently rescued the vector transmission of rice stripe virus
395 (Lu, Li et al. 2019). The same authors further demonstrated that the two proteins can interact
396 with the virus particle. NSvc2-N connects it to a putative receptor at the surface of the insect
397 gut cells and triggers endocytosis. NSvc2-C subsequently allows the release of the virion-
398 NSvc2-N complex from endosomes into the cytosol, presumably through a membrane fusion
399 activity whose precise mode of action remains elusive in the specific case of tenuiviruses (Lu,
400 Li et al. 2019)(Figure 2a).

401 These results are seemingly compatible with the bridge hypothesis, at least for NSvc2-N (Yao,
402 Liu et al. 2014), but some aspects need further investigations. In particular, it is unclear
403 whether NSvc2-C can be acquired sequentially or whether a co-acquisition with the virion
404 and/or NSvc2-N is mandatory. Because Gn and Gc of bunyaviruses are generally forming

405 heterodimers (Hepojoki, Strandin et al. 2010), it would also be interesting to test a possible
406 co-acquisition of NSvc2-N and NSvc2-C as a unique complex that could complement the
407 ulterior acquisition and transmission of purified viral particles.

408 Nanoviruses

409 Analogous to approaches earlier developed for non-circulative poty- or caulimoviruses (see
410 section 2), Franz and coworkers discovered that the aphid transmission of purified faba bean
411 necrotic yellows virus (FBNYV, genus *Nanovirus*) particles was not possible, unless the aphid
412 vectors were previously fed on a plant infected by a transmissible isolate (Franz, van der Wilk
413 et al. 1999; Table 1). Similar pre-feeding on an infected plant was also required for the
414 transmission of purified viral particles directly injected into the aphid hemolymph. Although its
415 viral origin was not proven, the authors concluded that a HC was most likely produced in
416 infected plants and necessary for the virus to cross the gut and salivary gland cell barriers.
417 Unfortunately, both the identity and the mode of action of this putative HC remained
418 unexplored after this seminal work, even long after infectious clones of nanoviruses became
419 available.

420 The family *Nanoviridae* regroups viruses composed of six (genus *Babuvirus*) or eight (genus
421 *Nanovirus*) ssDNA genomic segments, individually encapsidated in distinct viral particles and
422 each encoding a single protein (Gronenborn 2004; Lal, Vo et al. 2020). Infectious clones could
423 be successfully produced for several member species of the genus *Nanovirus* (Timchenko,
424 Katul et al. 2006; Grigoras, Timchenko et al. 2009; Grigoras, Ginzo et al. 2014; Grigoras,
425 Vetten et al. 2018), but so far failed for babuviruses. Because of the nature of these infectious
426 constructs, one clone per genomic segment, these authors realized that some segments could
427 be omitted upon inoculation without compromising the systemic infection of host plants
428 (Timchenko, Katul et al. 2006; Grigoras, Vetten et al. 2018). They were then able to
429 demonstrate that in the absence of the segment N, the host plant appeared systemically
430 infected but aphid transmission from this plant was impossible (Grigoras, Vetten et al. 2018).
431 Modifications of the start codon or coding sequence further showed that the HC of nanoviruses
432 is not the segment N itself but its encoded NSP protein (Grigoras, Vetten et al. 2018; Di Mattia,
433 Vernerey et al. 2020).

434 The localization of the coat protein of banana bunchy top babuvirus in its aphid vector
435 indicated that the virus accumulates at only two locations, the anterior midgut and the principal
436 salivary glands (Bressan and Watanabe 2011; Watanabe and Bressan 2013). Di Mattia and
437 co-workers (Di Mattia, Vernerey et al. 2020) recently re-investigated this localization for faba
438 bean necrotic stunt virus (FBNSV, genus *Nanovirus*), in the presence/absence of the segment
439 N. Not only did they observe that this segment was mandatory for the internalization of the

440 virus and its accumulation in the aphid gut cells, but also that the NSP protein colocalized
 441 therein with both viral DNA and coat protein. This observation is reminiscent of that described
 442 for NSvc2-N of tenuiviruses (Lu, Li et al. 2019) and again compatible with the bridge
 443 hypothesis. The NSP protein may attach to the viral particles on one side and to a gut (and/or
 444 salivary gland) cell receptor on the other side and trigger the endocytosis of the complex (Di
 445 Mattia, Vernerey et al. 2020). However, most recent incongruent observations are now casting
 446 doubts (Figure 2b).

447

448

449 **Figure 2: Schematization of the hypothetical mode of action of HC for circulative viruses**
 450 **transmitted by hemipteran insects.** The mode of action of HC in circulative propagative transmission
 451 of tenuiviruses is summarized on the left. The mode of action of the HC of circulative non propagative
 452 nanoviruses is shown on the right.

453

454 A thorough characterization of protein-protein interactions was conducted between the eight
 455 proteins of another nanovirus, the pea necrotic yellow dwarf virus (PNYDV), using bimolecular
 456 fluorescence complementation (BiFC; (Krenz, Schießl et al. 2017). This approach revealed

457 that NSP interacts with itself and with M-Rep (the replication-associated protein) but,
458 surprisingly, not with the coat protein CP. Because an interaction between NSP and CP has
459 since then been reported for babuviruses (Ji, Yu et al. 2019; Yu N 2019), this question
460 deserves further investigation for nanoviruses. In the BiFC system, the fusion of fluorescent
461 reporter protein to NSP may have hindered the interaction with CP.

462 One highly consistent observation on the action of HCs in non-circulative transmission is that
463 it must be acquired first, prior to the virus particles, the reverse acquisition sequence being
464 systematically inefficient. This has always been interpreted as related to the capacity of the
465 helper to recognize its receptor in the vector mouthparts or foregut, while the virus particle
466 cannot directly do this and is thus “flushed” with the digestive flux/transit when acquired first
467 and alone. Recent work from our laboratory yielded a contradicting observation (Di Mattia,
468 Torralba et al. 2022). As mentioned above, some genome segments of nanoviruses can be
469 omitted at inoculation of host plants and we made use of this possibility to design sequential
470 acquisition experiments. Plants infected with either the segment N or the segment U4 missing
471 (respectively named FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ and FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾) exhibit symptoms similar to those resulting
472 from wild type FBNSV infection, and FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾ is perfectly transmissible by aphid while
473 FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ is not (Grigoras, Vetten et al. 2018). According to the current understanding of the
474 mode of action of HCs, aphids fed first on the FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾ plants should acquire NSP and
475 subsequently complement the acquisition and transmission of the segment U4 from FBNSV-
476 N⁽⁻⁾ plants. In contrast, in the reverse acquisition sequence, U4-containing virus particles
477 should not be internalized in and transmitted by aphid, due to the absence of NSP protein in
478 the first acquisition from FBNSV-N⁽⁻⁾ plants, and due to their absence in the second acquisition
479 from FBNSV-U4⁽⁻⁾ plants. To our surprise, U4 segment was as efficiently internalized in and
480 transmitted by aphids whatever the sequence of acquisition (Di Mattia, Torralba et al 2022).
481 This proved true even when aphids were “purged” on healthy plants for up to 2 days in
482 between the two acquisition phases. This observation is very intriguing and is further
483 discussed in the last section. It demonstrates that, in the case of nanoviruses, the HC can
484 expectedly wait for virions within the aphid, but that the virions can somewhat unexpectedly
485 wait for the HC for at least two days without being flushed out by the digestive flux.

486 **5 Conclusion**

487 5.1 What is a helper component

488 When Froissart and colleagues (Froissart, Michalakis et al. 2002) proposed the extended
489 definition of HC, the helper-dependent strategy was almost exclusively described for non-
490 circulative viruses. Most knowledge on the nature and mode of action of HCs were based on
491 the thorough characterization of the best-studied cases, P2 of CaMV and HC-Pro of

492 potyviruses, but the proposed definition also accounted for the fragmentary data on HCs of
493 other virus groups available at that time (Table 1). Since then, additional reports have been
494 published, the most intriguing being those confirming the existence of the helper strategy in
495 circulative transmission (Grigoras, Vetten et al. 2018; Lu, Li et al. 2019; Di Mattia, Torralba et
496 al 2022). In all cases, HCs are non-structural proteins encoded by the virus and they are
497 mandatory for the success of vectors transmission. One key feature of HCs that is confronted
498 by these recent findings is the sequential acquisition of HC and virions. While the sequential
499 acquisition was always shown to be possible solely if the HC is acquired first, the study of a
500 circulative nanovirus (Di Mattia, Torralaba et al 2022) proved that the reverse sequence also
501 works in this viral system. At this stage, it is not clear whether this observation is inherent to a
502 distinct mode of action of HCs in circulative viruses, because the only other HC characterized
503 for another circulative virus, the phenuivirus RSV (Lu, Li et al. 2019), has not been tested
504 when acquired after the virus particles.

505 The sequential acquisition has been proposed as a key feature of HCs because it allows HC-
506 trans-complementation, *e.i.* the HC encoded by a genome X in a virus population can assist
507 the transmission of a genome Y from the same population or from another population in
508 another host plant, allowing cooperation between related viral genomes at the transmission
509 step rather than competition (Pirone and Blanc 1996). It is noticeable that, in this view, the
510 sequence of acquisition does not matter, and so the current definition of HCs still perfectly
511 holds for all cases reported thus far.

512 5.2 How does a helper component work

513 The sole mode of action of HCs reported to date is the bridge hypothesis extensively described
514 in previous sections. This hypothesis derives from the observation that HCs have to be present
515 for the virus particle to be efficiently retained or internalized in the vector. Without HC, virions
516 are supposedly flushed together with the flux in the digestive track, explaining why the HC
517 have to be acquired either prior to or together with the virus particles. Clearly, the fact that the
518 HC of nanoviruses (the NSP protein) can efficiently mediate the aphid transmission of virus
519 particles acquired several days ahead is questioning its mode of action. The virus particles
520 could somehow be retained within the gut lumen of aphid vectors and be internalized and
521 accumulate within epithelial gut cells solely through the action of the protein NSP. This is
522 opening several possibilities that are calling for further investigation. The virus particles could
523 be retained in the gut lumen non-specifically, embedded in gut cell secretions or stuck in
524 between the microvilli, but they could also be specifically attached to membrane receptors.
525 Investigating the viral determinants of nanovirus-aphid specificity would answer this question.
526 Then the NSP protein acquired later could trigger endocytosis of virions or of NSP-virion
527 complexes. Additional role of NSP in transcytosis, and release of virus particles into the

528 hemolymph are also conceivable and would all represent a mode of action significantly distinct
529 from the classical bridge hypothesis.

530

531 5.3 Why are helper components so frequently involved in the vector transmission of plant 532 viruses

533 The distinction between capsid and helper strategies in vector-transmission of viruses has
534 been conceptualized and empirically studied solely in plant virology. The requirement of an
535 HC for successful virus-vector interaction have been confirmed countless times, on totally
536 unrelated viruses, transmitted by unrelated vectors, through very different mechanisms
537 (Hogenhout, Ammar el et al. 2008, Dietzgen, Mann et al. 2016, Lu, Li et al. 2019). Therefore,
538 the helper strategy certainly evolved several times independently, indicating that it likely
539 confers a selective benefit, at least in some environmental conditions. Paradoxically, because
540 it requires the production of an additional viral protein to ensure virus transmission, the helper
541 strategy may incur a cost to the virus when compared to the capsid strategy. However, some
542 HCs interact with various partners (other viral, host plant or vector molecules) at different steps
543 of the virus cycle, either in the vector or within the host plant where they ensure important and
544 diverse functions. A case study is the multi-tasking protein HC-Pro of potyvirids involved in
545 many different processes (Valli, Gallo et al. 2018). This multifunctionality may compensate the
546 cost associated to the maintenance of a helper protein, and may instead confer specific benefit
547 to viruses. But, not all HCs are known to be multifunctional and so the benefit they may provide
548 remains largely elusive. Their possible multifarious mode of action in distinct viral clades may
549 stem from the fact that each of these clades have evolved HCs with their own molecular
550 means, and thus the question of whether the selective pressure that drove this evolution are
551 similar in all cases is an interesting issue. In other words, whether all HCs have been selected
552 for the same reason, and for what reason, is a complete mystery for which some speculations
553 are provided below.

554 Cooperation hypothesis

555 A long-standing proposition is that HCs could result from selection at the quasispecies/virus
556 population level (Pirone and Blanc 1996). According to these authors, HC allows cooperation
557 between genomes of a viral population (or of distinct populations located in different host
558 plants) during vector transmission, whereas the capsid strategy does not. If a genome within
559 a population produces a HC that is adapted to the dominant vector species in a given place
560 and at a given time, it will assist the transmission of other genomes acquired through HC-
561 Trans-complementation that do not produce such adapted HC. The consequence is the
562 relaxing of the bottleneck associated to selection by the vector and maintenance of a higher

563 polymorphisms in the transmitted populations. This hypothetical benefit could apply to all virus
564 species with the helper strategy, but unfortunately no experimental support has been provided,
565 and a way to test for it is even hard to imagine.

566 Collective transmission hypothesis

567 An important proportion (that can be up to 100%) of virions from viral populations of most virus
568 species appears to contain defective genomes (for reviews on defective particles see (Sun
569 and Brooke 2018; Vignuzzi and Lopez 2019), or only part of the genetic information (for a
570 review on multipartite virus see (Michalakis and Blanc 2020), resulting in a possible benefit of
571 co-transmitting several particles to the same host (or cell within this host) in order to restore
572 infectivity. This view of a viral infectious unit as a “collective infectious unit” has been reviewed
573 countless times recently, and in particular the mechanisms through which viruses can achieve
574 collective transmission (Sanjuan 2017; Sanjuan 2018; Leeks, Sanjuan et al. 2019; Sanjuan
575 and Thoulouze 2019; Shirogane, Watanabe et al. 2019). While the mechanisms invoked
576 include the incorporation of several genomes in the same capsid (bacteriophage), the passage
577 of large amounts of virus particles through virus-induced nanotubes connecting distinct cells
578 or through membrane vesicles transferring in viral synapses (HIV, Influenza, Herpesvirus), the
579 formation of virion aggregates with spontaneous binding between particles (vesicular
580 stomatitis virus), or the multi-virion complexes found in occlusion bodies of baculoviruses, HCs
581 have not been hypothesized to potentially facilitate collective transmission. Most characterized
582 HC have been demonstrated to bind the virus coat protein (Blanc, Lopez-Moya et al. 1997;
583 Peng, Kadoury et al. 1998; Plisson, Uzest et al. 2005; Hoh, Uzest et al. 2010; Ji, Yu et al.
584 2019; Lu, Li et al. 2019; Yu N 2019) and to also self-interact (Hébrard, Drucker et al. 2001;
585 Ruiz-Ferrer, Boskovic et al. 2005; Krenz, SchieSsl et al. 2017), and thus to possibly trigger
586 aggregation of virus particles. For example, we have demonstrated that the genome segments
587 of nanoviruses acquired simultaneously (Di Mattia, Vernerey et al. 2020) or even sequentially
588 (Di Mattia, Torralaba et al 2022) by the aphid vector accumulate all together in the same
589 intracellular aggregates in the AMG cells solely if a functional segment N encoding the NSP
590 protein is present in infected plants. Nanoviruses being multipartite, collective transmission of
591 several viral particles may appear immediately beneficial (Michalakis et Blanc 2020).
592 However, HCs have been described in very numerous monopartite viruses, suggesting that,
593 under this hypothesis, collective transmission would be beneficial whatever the genome
594 architecture/organization.

595 The effector hypothesis

596 When entering a cell, viruses have to manipulate its defenses to initiate infection (Wu, Valli et
597 al. 2019). This is true for many intracellular pathogens, including bacteria and fungi, which

598 release effector proteins hampering cell-defense and facilitating infection. When injected into
599 a new plant by a vector, one viral protein that is first in contact with the host cell is the coat
600 protein. While its putative contribution to counter cell defenses has been envisaged and
601 discussed (Conti, Rodriguez et al. 2017; Nicaise and Candresse 2017; Wu, Valli et al. 2019),
602 that HCs could also be released together with virions and act as very early pathogen effectors
603 has not been envisaged. Most if not all HCs of non-circulative and circulative viruses could be
604 multifunctional proteins. Beyond constituting a molecular bridge linking the virus particles to
605 vector receptors, HCs also frequently have additional features that could reveal effector
606 activity. Again, the emblematic example is the HC-Pro of potyviruses that can hinder the plant
607 RNAi machinery, but other HCs, less understood, can also block the microtubular network (P2
608 of CaMV; Bak, Gargani et al. 2013), induce membrane fusion (NSvc2C of RSV; Lu, Li et al.
609 2019) or interact with stress granules (NSP of PNYDV; Krapp, Greiner et al. 2017). That they
610 interact with highly symmetrically arranged coat proteins, either icosahedral or helical, offers
611 multiple attachment sites per particle and ensures that a high number of HCs can potentially
612 be retained in and be released from the vector together with virions. The amount of HC
613 molecules delivered could even be larger when HCs are prone to self-oligomerization as is
614 the case for HC-Pro of potyviruses (Ruiz-Ferrer, Boskovic et al. 2005), P2 of CaMV
615 (Thornbury, Hellmann et al. 1985; Hébrard, Drucker et al. 2001; Plisson, Drucker et al. 2003),
616 NSP of nanoviruses (Krenz, SchieSSL et al. 2017) and NSvc2 of RSV (Lu, Li et al. 2019).
617 Hence, mobilizing a limited number of receptors in the vector may allow hundreds of HC
618 molecules to be retained and/or internalized and later inoculated into the plant. The present
619 paradigm regarding the primary role of an HC could thus completely change by considering
620 that it could be an effector useful to the virus upon arrival in a cell and that its binding to the
621 virus particles and to the vector would merely ensure that it travels and is delivered with it.
622 Whether HCs are released together with virions within host plant cells is not known but
623 investigation of this question would be relevant for this hypothesis. It is also important to note
624 that the “effector” hypothesis could apply to all HCs described thus far, and that the effector
625 function may either act in host plant cells, in vector cells, or both.

626 In conclusion, several potential benefits associated to the helper strategy are imaginable. We
627 insisted in this conclusion that each of this benefit could apply to all cases described, whatever
628 the viral clade concerned. However, we cannot exclude that distinct helpers have evolved for
629 distinct reasons and perhaps, other potential explanation are still to be conceived.
630 Unfortunately, as they stand, the here-described hypothesis, with perhaps the exception of
631 the “effector hypothesis” are not empirically testable, maintaining the question of the *raison-*
632 *d'être* of HCs a major conceptual challenge for future research in plant virology and vector
633 transmission.

Table 1: List of viral families and genera where HCs have been identified

Virus family ^a	Virus genus ^a	Virus name/acronym ^a	HC name/acronym	Transmission mode	Vector taxon	First HC-describing reference
<i>Potyviridae</i>	<i>Potyvirus</i>	Potato virus Y (PVY)	Helper-component proteinase (HC-Pro)	Non-circulative	Aphids	Kassanis and Govier 1971a,b
	<i>Tritimovirus</i>	Sweet potato mild mottle virus (SPMMV)			Whiteflies	Colinet et al 1998
	<i>Ipomovirus</i>	Wheat streak mosaic virus (WSMV)			Mites	Stenger et al 2005
<i>Caulimoviridae</i>	<i>Caulimovirus</i>	Cauliflower mosaic virus (CaMV)	Aphid transmission factor (P2)		Aphids	Lung and Pirone 1973
<i>Virgaviridae</i>	<i>Tobravirus</i>	Tobacco rattle virus (TBRV)	Protein 2b		Nematodes	McFarlane et al 1996
<i>Phenuiviridae</i>	<i>Tenuivirus</i>	Rice stripe virus (RSV)	Non-structural glycoprotein 2 (NSvc2)	Circulative propagative	Plant hoppers	Lu et al 2019
<i>Nanoviridae</i>	<i>Babuvirus</i>	Faba bean necrotic yellows virus (FBNSV)	Nuclear shuttle protein (NSP)	Circulative non-propagative	Aphids	Franz et al 1999
	<i>Nanovirus^b</i>					

^a Families and genera listed in this table are only those where the HC has been identified. The existence of an HC has been suggested in others but not identified.

^b Babuviruses have a DNA segment highly homologous to the segment N (encoding NSP) of nanoviruses and so its role as a HC makes little doubt though the lack of infectious clones has precluded definitive proof thus far.

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